

**BILINGUAL EDUCATION IN THE CRIMEA AS AN EFFECTIVE
MEANS OF MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE
GENÇLERİN ÇOK KÜLTÜRLÜ EĞİTİMİNDE ETKİLİ BİR ARAÇ
OLARAK KIRIM'DA ÇİFT DİLLİ EĞİTİM**

Natalya Yevgenyevna Selezneva¹

Article Type: Research Article

Abstract

The work is dedicated to the acute problem of developing the bilingual education in such historically, politically, ethnically and geographically unique region of the Russian Federation as the Republic of Crimea in the framework of realizing the provided by law right of the citizens to receive education in their native language, as well as improving the quality of foreign language education in middle and high school from the point of view of the socio-cultural approach. General scientific methods of theoretical analysis, observation, generalization, and concretization have been used to analyze the scientific articles in periodicals, dissertations, didactic materials on teaching a foreign language in bilingual schools. The article highlights the issues of history, nature and the state of bilingual education in Crimea. The importance of bilingual education as an effective means of multicultural education of youth in conditions of integration of Russia into the world economic and educational environment, and globalization of modern society is emphasized. The performed study shows that alongside the growing popularity and importance, bilingual education in Crimean region obtains new challenges and difficulties, especially concerning professional training of language teachers and logistical support of bilingual education, which can be solved by means of organizing special courses, seminars, webinars, foreign internship both for practicing and future teachers, professional communities of teachers, and modernizing teaching facilities, materials, and aids.

Keywords: Bilingual education, Multicultural education, Internationalization, Globalization, Integration into the world economic and educational environment

Öz

Bu çalışma, Rusya Federasyonu'nun Kırım Cumhuriyeti gibi tarihi, siyasi, etnik ve coğrafi olarak benzersiz bir bölgesinde, vatandaşların yasalarla sağlanan eğitim alma hakkının gerçekleştirilmesi için iki dilli eğitimin gelişimi durumunu ele almaktadır. Bununla birlikte ana dilin ortaokul ve lisede verilen yabancı dil eğitiminin niteliğini sosyo-kültürel yaklaşım açısından geliştirmesi durumu da araştırma kapsamına alınmıştır. İki dilli okullarda yabancı dil öğretimi ile ilgili süreli yayınlardaki bilimsel makaleleri, tezleri, didaktik materyallerini analiz etmek için bilimsel teorik analiz, gözlem, genelleme ve somutlaştırma yöntemleri kullanılmıştır. Bu makale, Kırım'da tarih, doğa ve iki dilli eğitimin durumu gibi konuları vurgulamaktadır. Rusya'nın dünya ekonomik ve eğitim ortamına entegrasyonu ve modern toplumun küreselleşmesi koşullarında gençlerin çok kültürlü eğitiminin etkili bir aracı olarak iki dilli eğitimin önemi vurgulanmaktadır. Yapılan çalışma Kırım bölgesinin artan popülaritesi ve önemine rağmen iki dilli eğitimin yeni zorluklar getirdiğini göstermektedir.

¹ Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor, Professor of the Foreign Languages Department, P.S. Nakhimov Black Sea Higher Naval School, Sevastopol, Russian Federation, natashaseleznyova@yahoo.co.uk

Özellikle dil öğretmenlerinin mesleki eğitimi ve iki dilli eğitimin lojistik desteği ile ilgili olarak özel kurslar, seminerler, düzenleyerek çözülebileceği görülmektedir. Web seminerleri hem uygulayıcı hem de geleceğin öğretmenleri için yabancı stajlar, profesyonel öğretmen toplulukları ve öğretim tesislerinin, materyallerinin ve yardımcılarının modernleştirilmesi de diğer çözüm yollarıdır.

Anahtar Sözcükler

İki dilli eğitim, Çok kültürlü eğitim, Uluslararasılaşma, Küreelleşme, Dünya ekonomik ve eğitim çevreleriyle entegrasyon

1. INTRODUCTION

In terms of modernization of the Russian educational system special importance is given not only to the problem of improving the quality of foreign language education in middle and high school but also to the development of bilingual education as a means to enhance linguistic pluralism in teaching foreign languages, one of the socio-pedagogical ways of resolving the contradictions of modern cultural development of countries and peoples, containing the significant potential of multicultural education of young people.

As Shirin (2007) notes in his thesis, bilingual education gets a special role as a technological and methodological framework of the internationalization of secondary and higher education in the Bologna process. Sorochkina (2000) states that in bilingual education foreign language is transformed from the learning objective into means of acquiring special knowledge and multicultural education.

At present, the problems of bilingual education are examined from the point of view of psychology, linguistics, pedagogy, didactics, and on an interdisciplinary level. Vorobyova and Grabbe (2016), considering the issues of formation of communicative bilingual personality, noted that a comprehensive study of the issue of bilingualism is only possible in the interaction of communicative linguistics and linguistic didactics. Analysis of research works shows that Russian researchers of the 21st century are interested in such questions as the influence of bilingualism on linguistic personality (Znamenskaya, 2014), bilingual education of preschool children (Ivanova, 2013), the use of innovative strategies, methods, and techniques of bilingual education (Abramova & Yessina, 2014), development trends (Dudnikova, 2017), etc.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Dissertations and scientific articles in Russian periodicals on bilingual education over the past 20 years, as well as didactic materials on teaching a foreign language in Crimean bilingual schools, have been studied. General scientific methods of theoretical analysis of research works, observation of teaching practice in Crimean bilingual schools, generalization and concretization of the scientific notions and findings on the issue under discussion have been used.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For the first time the notions of "bilingualism", "bilingual training" and "bilingual education" appeared in the scientific literature in the 1990s, and in 1994 the concept of bilingual education was approved by UNESCO (as cited in Hudobina, 2005, p. 161). There are many studies of the nature and typology of bilingualism, often replaced by a synonym "two-linguism", which is understood as the possession of at least two languages in equal or varying degrees. Most scientists believe that bilingualism can be natural and artificial, although some scholars have identified up to 30 types of bilingualism (Abramova & Yessina, 2014; Vorobyova & Grabbe, 2016; Znamenskaya, 2014; Hudobina, 2005). Under bilingual education Hudobina (2005, p. 162) understands acquiring samples and values of the world culture by means of native and foreign languages, when the foreign language acts as a way of learning the world specific knowledge, assimilation of the cultural, historical, and social experience of different countries and peoples.

Bilingual education includes 1) the interconnected use of two languages as a means of educational activities when learning the subject and acquiring subject knowledge in a particular field; 2) learning a foreign language in the process of mastering certain subject knowledge through the use of two languages and language acquisition as means of educational activities (Abramova & Yessina, 2014; Dudnikova, 2017). The second language is the object of learning, means of communication, and language of teaching.

Bilingual education, which implies an active practice of teaching in two languages simultaneously, is most widely applied in educational institutions of the countries where there are several languages used by the society, such as the USA, Canada, Germany, Russia etc.

Among the main benefits of implementing bilingual education researchers define:

- achieving a high level of subject, language, intercultural competence of students;
- increasing motivation in learning a foreign language;
- increased competitiveness of students and thus the improvement of career prospects;
- development of cognitive abilities;
- learning and developing tolerance to other cultures, analysis of your own culture (Dudnikova, 2017; Ivanova, 2013; Piterskaja, 2015).

However, bilingual education has also its disadvantages:

- there is a possibility of full assimilation with another culture and the loss of connection to the native culture;
- the successful formation of bilingual competence is closely linked to the professionalism of the training of educators, teachers, professors, but the problem of preparation of highly skilled experts is still to be solved (Ivanova, 2013; Piterskaja, 2015).

In the multicultural Crimea, the ideas of multicultural and bilingual education are under

increasing development. Such bilingual educational institutions of the Crimea should be mentioned as:

- 1) Simferopol academic gymnasium with Russian (grades 1-10) and Ukrainian (grades 4-10) languages of education;
- 2) Municipal budget educational institution "Ukrainian school" of the Simferopol area of the Crimea, where the training is implemented in Russian (grades 1-10) and in the Crimean Tatar language (grade 4);
- 3) Private educational establishment "Simferopol International School", founded in 2003. It provides education in Humanities through an in-depth study of foreign languages, bilingual teaching of subjects of a natural-mathematical cycle, and foreign language philology. According to the academic programs of the school, the main objective of the bilingual education is the formation and development of communicative competence in conjunction with speaking and linguistic competence (Avilova, 2017).

The content of the training has the following features:

- from 1st class foreign language (English) and computer science are taught;
- from 3rd class a second foreign language (Turkish) is studied;
- from 7th class bilingual education (in mathematics, physics and chemistry are studied in Russian and English languages) begins;
- from 10th class training in foreign language philology is available.

Extracurricular activities include school groups (theater, music, visual art, choreography), sports (tennis, wrestling, volleyball, soccer), electives (French, German, Crimean Tatar).

- 4) In the Crimean boarding school gymnasium for gifted children in the village of Tankovoye, Bakhchisaray district specialized in English language training, whose graduates enter universities not only in Russia but also in Ukraine, Poland, Turkey, Canada, USA and UK, teaching five subjects - science, mathematics, physics, chemistry and biology - is conducted in the English and Russian languages. It is definitely a powerful factor in the development of children's intellectual abilities.
- 5) "Bilingual gymnasium №2" is one of the oldest educational institutions in the city of Sevastopol, founded in 1874, in 2016 ranked in the list of 500 best schools of Russia. It is a school of Humanities, where bilingual education is provided in: Russian-French and Russian-Ukrainian.
- 6) "Secondary School № 3 with profound studying of the English language" (Sevastopol).
- 7) Secondary School № 5 with Russian and Crimean Tatar languages of education (Bakhchisaray).

- 8) Kindergarten "Vishenka" in Bakhchisaray district, where teaching is conducted in the Russian and Crimean Tatar languages.
- 9) Kindergarten "Gnyozdyshko" (Bakhchisaray) with the Russian and Crimean Tatar languages of education, etc.

Thus, it can be stated that bilingual education is being widely implemented in the educational practice of Crimea at all levels of education – from high schools to preschools. Humanities, science and math cycle subjects teaching in English, German, French are used in secondary schools. In kindergartens and secondary schools, the predominant pattern is the realization of the right of citizens to receive education in their native language, as provided by law. In this regard, in a number of schools there are classes with Crimean Tatar and Ukrainian languages of education. In kindergartens children learn Crimean Tatar language in the form of a game, classes are conducted in two languages.

However, as the observation of the teaching practice in the Crimean bilingual educational establishments shows, the main problems they are facing are lack of 1) highly professional personnel, and 2) means and materials for teaching languages at the level that would meet the demands of the modern education.

To solve these problems, the following measures would be effective:

- development of special courses on bilingual education for students of foreign languages and pedagogical institutions;
- organization of special courses, seminars, webinars, foreign internship for practicing teachers as a part of their professional development program;
- encouraging establishment of professional societies, communities, and groups of bilingual school teachers to exchange their experience, achievements and hardships – real and virtual (via Internet);
- developing and publishing up-to-date teaching materials and aids for bilingual education at all levels for different languages and subjects;
- setting up special language or self-study classrooms.

4. CONCLUSION

The performed study shows that bilingual education in the Crimean region is gaining its popularity and importance, and corresponds to the realization of the right of the citizens to receive education in their native language (Russian, Ukrainian, and Crimean Tatar), as provided by law. It enhances not only mastering the mother tongue of different ethnic groups of the republic and a foreign language (English, German, French prevailing), but acquiring a foreign culture, which meets the demands of the current Russian education modernization process. Nevertheless, the system of bilingual education in Crimea faces problems, the most

acute of which are professional training of teachers and logistical support of bilingual education. They can be solved by means of organizing special courses, seminars, webinars, foreign internship both for practicing and future teachers, professional communities of teachers, and modernizing teaching facilities, materials, and aids.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- Abramova, N.V., Yessina, I.Yu. (2014). Innovacionnye strategii v bilingval'nom obuchenii [Innovative Strategies in Bilingual Training] / *Fundamental'nye Issledovaniya [Fundamental Research]*, 6-2, 345-349. [in Russian]
- Avilova, I.E. (2017). Rabochaya programma po predmetu «Nemeckij jazyk» (osnovnoe obshhee obrazovanie, 5-a, b, v klassy) [Syllabus on subject "German Language", secondary education, 5 a, b, c class], Simferopol', 18 p. [in Russian]
- Bilinguism and its Influence on Linguistic Personality]. *Innovacii v obrazovatel'nyh uchrezhdeniyah [Innovations in Educational Establishments]*, 3, 42-46. [in Russian]
- Dudnikova, S.D. (2017). Bilingval'noe obuchenie i tendencii ego razvitiya [Bilingual Training and Tendencies of its Development] <https://infourok.ru/statya-bilingvalnoe-obuchenie-i-tendencii-ego-razvitiya-1726723.html> [in Russian]
- Hudobina, O.F. (2005). Bilingval'noe obrazovanie kak mezhdisciplinarny fenomen [Bilingual Education as Interdisciplinary Phenomenon]. *Izvestija VolgGTU [News of VolgGTU]*, 5, 161-163. [in Russian]
- Ivanova, N.V. (2013). Bilingval'noe obrazovanie doshkol'nikov [Bilingual Education of Preschoolers]. *Sovremennyye problemy nauki i obrazovaniya [Modern Problems of Science and Education]*, 4. <https://science-education.ru/ru/article/view?id=9987> [in Russian]
- Piterskaja, S.Je. (2015). Obuchenie na bilingval'noy osnove v uslovyjah mezhhkul'turnoy kommunikacii [Bilingual-based Education in Intercultural Communication]. *Sovremennaja pedagogika [Modern Pedagogics]*, 5. <http://pedagogika.snauka.ru/2015/05/4410> (accessed: 01.10.2017). [in Russian]
- Shirin, A.G. (2007). Bilingval'noe obrazovanie v otechestvennoy i zarubezhnoy pedagogike [Bilingual Education in Native and Foreign Pedagogics] [Abstract of Doctoral dissertation, V. Novgorod], 56 p. [in Russian]
- Sorochkina, N.I. (2000) Integral'naya model' bilingval'nogo obucheniya v sovremennoy rossiyskoy shkole [Integral Model of Bilingual Education in Modern Russian School] [Doctoral dissertation, V. Novgorod], 228 p. [in Russian]
- Vorobyova, O.V., Grabbe, N.Yu. (2016). Osobennosti bilingvizma pri dvujazychii [Peculiarities of Bilingualism in Bilingualism]. *Nauchnyj Zhurnal KubGAU [Scientific Journal of KubSAU]*, 119(05). <http://ej.kubagro.ru/2016/05/pdf/57.pdf> [in Russian]
- Znamenskaja, T.A. (2014). Problemy bilingvizma i ego vliyaniya na yazykovyju lichnost' [Problems of Bilinguism and its Influence on Linguistic Personality]. *Innovacii v obrazovatel'nyh uchrezhdeniyah [Innovations in Educational Establishments]*, 3, 42-46. [in Russian]